

C-IMMSIM simulation results

November 11, 2024

Abstract

This document includes the plots relative to the simulation and the outcome of the epitope/peptide prediction used.

Produced by the C-IMMSIM Online server available at
<http://c-immsim.iac.rm.cnr.it> (alias to <http://kraken.iac.rm.cnr.it/C-IMMSIM>)

CITATIONS: For publication of results, please cite the following:

Nicolas Rapin, Ole Lund, Massimo Bernaschi, Filippo Castiglione. Computational Immunology Meets Bioinformatics: The Use of Prediction Tools for Molecular Binding in the Simulation of the Immune System. PLoS ONE 5(4): e9862
doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0009862, 2010

A retrospective validation

In-silico evaluation of adenoviral COVID-19 vaccination protocols: Assessment of immunological memory up to 6 months after the third dose. P. Stolfi, F. Castiglione, E. Mastrostefano, I. Di Biase, S. Di Biase, G. Palmieri, A. Prisco. Frontiers in Immunology, 13 (2022) doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2022.998262
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fimmu.2022.998262>

An in vivo validation

Identification and validation of viral antigens sharing sequence and structural homology with tumor associated antigens (TAAs). C. Ragone, C. Manolio, B. Cavalluzzo, A. Petrizzo, A. Mauriello, M-L. Tornesello, F. M. Buonaguro, F. Castiglione, L. Vitagliano, M. Ruvo, M. Tagliamonte, L. Buonaguro. Journal for ImmunoTherapy of Cancer. 9:e002694 (2021)
<https://jitc.bmj.com/content/9/5/e002694>

Original C-IMMSIM model: www.iac.cnr.it/~filippo/c-immsim

GETTING HELP:

Scientific problems: Filippo Castiglione (filippo dot castiglione at cnr dot it)

Technical problems: Ilaria Gonnella (ilaria dot gonnella at cnr dot it)

Figure 1: Cell counts shown. Legend: Act=active, Intern=internalized the Ag, Pres II = presenting on MHC II, Dup = in the mitotic cycle, Anergic = anergic, Resting = not active.

Figure 2: Legend: symbols as figure above.

Figure 3: The virus, the immunoglobulins and the immunocomplexes.

Figure 4: Concentration of cytokines and interleukins. Inset plot shows danger signal together with leukocyte growth factor IL-2.

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/23212_20241111-063535_5_MsQkb3budZQD.FSA_1_001

MEAAAKGIINTLQKYYCRVRGGRCAVLSCLPKKEEQIGKCTRGRKCCRKKSSSLKTVDTITLSSLKVKDSSQPKSLLL
ALWELHVSSLMLLALWELHVSSLSMLPILILLSSLLSVAGFQMFVAAIYISLPVLLHAAAYFKPHISGIGAAAYFTASNIKI
VAAYYRLSINHSAAYFVDPVDLHMAAYVAGEQSAVEKHHHHHHH

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

0] pos= 179 score=0.017852 unnormalised=1.905600000 DVDLHMAAY
1] pos= -1 score=0.982148 unnormalised=104.841000000 non-binding event

Allele: B0702
Pseudo sequence: KAAREEQQIKAQTRE
Threshold: 8.702800
Max score: 28.406000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/23212_20241111-063535_5_MsQkb3budZQD.FSA_1_001

MEAAAKGIINTLQKYYCRVRGGRCAVLSCLPKKEEQIGKCTRGRKCCRKKSSSLKTVDTITLSSLKVKDSSQPKSLLL
ALWELHVSSLMLLALWELHVSSLSMLPILILLSSLLSVAGFQMFVAAIYISLPVLLHAAAYFKPHISGIGAAAYFTASNIKI
VAAYYRLSINHSAAYFVDPVDLHMAAYVAGEQSAVEKHHHHHHH

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

0] pos= -1 score=1.000000 unnormalised=104.841000000 non-binding event

Allele: B0702
Pseudo sequence: KAAREEQQIKAQTRE
Threshold: 8.702800
Max score: 28.406000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/23212_20241111-063535_5_MsQkb3budZQD.FSA_1_001

MEAAAKGIINTLQKYYCRVRGGRCAVLSCLPKKEEQIGKCTRGRKCCRKKSSSLKTVDTITLSSLKVKDSSQPKSLLL
ALWELHVSSLMLLALWELHVSSLSMLPILILLSSLLSVAGFQMFVAAIYISLPVLLHAAAYFKPHISGIGAAAYFTASNIKI
VAAYYRLSINHSAAYFVDPVDLHMAAYVAGEQSAVEKHHHHHHH

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DoPeptideList_II:

Given the antigen injected creates the list of peptides for all the
NumAgProts proteins and for all i.e., 2 MHCII molecules

Read class II peptide list from file? NO

Allele: DRB1_0101
Pseudo sequence: KFAHVEQRKAQTRV
Threshold: 2.392440

Max score: 26.461000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/23212_20241111-063535_5_MsQkb3budZQD.FSA_1_001

MEAAAKGIINTLQKYYCRVRGGRCVLSCLPKKEEQIGKCSTRGRKCCRKSSSLKTVDTITLSSLKVKDSSQPKSSLLL
ALWELHVSSMLLALWELHVSSLSMLPILILLSLLSVAGFQMFVAAYIYSLPVLHAAAYFKPHISGIGAAAYFTASNIKI
VAAAYRLSINHSVAAAYFVPDVLHMAAYVAGEQSAVEKHHHHHHH

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

0]	pos= 15	score=0.018302	unnormalised=3.2015600000	YCRVRGGRC
1]	pos= 82	score=0.037063	unnormalised=6.4835600000	WELHVSSLM
2]	pos= 95	score=0.033953	unnormalised=5.9395600000	WELHVSSLS
3]	pos= 99	score=0.011756	unnormalised=2.0565600000	VSSLSMLPI
4]	pos= 102	score=0.019657	unnormalised=3.4385600000	LSMLPILIL
5]	pos= 107	score=0.061547	unnormalised=10.7665600000	ILILLSSSL
6]	pos= 108	score=0.056545	unnormalised=9.8915600000	LILLSLLS
7]	pos= 111	score=0.047033	unnormalised=8.2275600000	LSSLLSVAG
8]	pos= 114	score=0.033056	unnormalised=5.7825600000	LLSVAGFQM
9]	pos= 120	score=0.043580	unnormalised=7.6235600000	FQMFVAAYI
10]	pos= 123	score=0.029163	unnormalised=5.1015600000	FVAAYIYSL
11]	pos= 127	score=0.057906	unnormalised=10.1295600000	YIYSLPVL
12]	pos= 144	score=0.004022	unnormalised=0.7035600000	ISGIGAAAYF
13]	pos= 151	score=0.035806	unnormalised=6.2635600000	YFTASNIKI
14]	pos= 157	score=0.014472	unnormalised=2.5315600000	IKIVAAYYR
15]	pos= 163	score=0.031890	unnormalised=5.5785600000	YRRLSINHS
16]	pos= 164	score=0.053252	unnormalised=9.3155600000	YRRLSINHSV
17]	pos= 166	score=0.016330	unnormalised=2.8565600000	LSINHSVAA
18]	pos= 182	score=0.001135	unnormalised=0.1985600000	LHMAAYVAG
19]	pos= 187	score=0.015283	unnormalised=2.6735600000	YVAGEQSAV
20]	pos= -1	score=0.378249	unnormalised=66.1680000000	non-binding event

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Max score: 26.461000

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MEAAAKGIINTLQKYYCRVRGGRCVLSCLPKKEEQIGKCSTRGRKCCRKSSSLKTVDTITLSSLKVKDSSQPKSSLLL
ALWELHVSSMLLALWELHVSSLSMLPILILLSLLSVAGFQMFVAAYIYSLPVLHAAAYFKPHISGIGAAAYFTASNIKI
VAAAYRLSINHSVAAAYFVPDVLHMAAYVAGEQSAVEKHHHHHHH

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